

Reading of Beatrice's Recollections of Memory in Kazuo Ishiguro's *The Buried Giant*

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Abstract

*Highly inspired by the fourteenth century Arthurian chivalric romance, Sir Gawain and the Green Knight, Ishiguro recorded the *The Buried Giant* on the collective memory and forgetting, concentrating more on "the blank period of British history." Recollections activate the mind moving towards the past journey of life to relive the happy moments or to learn lessons from the unwanted sufferings. There are two parallel lines interlinked to ensure the peace and nostalgia over the past memories. The first line carries the story of the couple Axl and his wife Beatrice who are in search of their son whom they believe to be alive. The second line tells the story of Sir Gawain, the Knight who tried to comprehend the morality between good and evil and the connection between present and past. Ishiguro has created a boatman Charon, the mythical character who would take the couple to the other island, the symbolical representation of Heaven or hell. Euphoria, the momentous joyfulness stays till untangling the mystery. Let the mystery stay as mystery to celebrate the existing joy of life and instructing the phantom of emotions to bury the giant of sorrows and reverberations due to grieves soulfully to stand the test of time.*

Keywords: collective memory, recollections, Charon, Euphoria.

Introduction

Kazuo Ishiguro, the Japanese born British Novelist, screen writer and a short story writer was awarded the Nobel Prize in literature 2017, and Booker Prize for his most renowned novel, *The Remains of the Day* with themes such as "memory, time, and self-delusion." His other works include *A Pale View of Hills* (1982), *Artist of the Floating world* (1986), *The Unconsold* (1995), *When we are orphans* (2000), *Never Let me go* (2005), and *The Buried Giant* (2015). The former Poet Laureate Andrew Motion has said that "Ishiguro's imaginative world has the great virtue and value of being simultaneously highly individual and deeply familiar— a world of puzzlement, isolation, watchfulness, threat and wonder." As Ishiguro feels that "memory is quite central" to him and he likes "the actual texture of writing through memory."

Ishiguro's *The Buried Giant* is a challenging work of medieval romance set in post Arthurian time's talks of the Sixth Century

King Arthur's reign. Highly inspired by the fourteenth century Arthurian chivalric romance, Sir Gawain and the Green Knight, Ishiguro recorded the *The Buried Giant* on the collective memory and forgetting, concentrating more on "the blank period of British history." Axl and Beatrice, an elderly Briton married couple traverse in the mainstream structure of the novel with their problems of memory loss. Everyone suffers from memory loss.

Recollections activate the mind moving towards the past journey of life to relive the happy moments or to learn lessons from the unwanted sufferings. In the former, recollection is a kind of willing journey to remember things with gratitude and reliving the ever loving moments of the lost life whereas in the latter, it becomes a caution not to repeat the unpardonable mistakes which had brought the ruin, a lesson to be taken from it. Recollection helps us on both ways to rejoice on our happy moments or to regret on our uncouth behaviours. It's a meditative moment wherein the soul analyses the presence of God. It needs a lot of self esteem and considerable mental discipline to accept ourselves with all good and bad actions. During the course of recollection, the action which is vibrant creates reverberation, creating persistence of moods and sounds depending on the incident showing optimum explanations. It creates a kind of storm and feelings, as it creates in music or sound.

There are two parallel lines interlinked to ensure the peace and nostalgia over the past memories. The first line carries the story of the couple Axl and his wife Beatrice who are in search of their son whom they believe to be alive. The second line tells the story of Sir Gawain, the Knight who tried to comprehend the morality between good and evil and the connection between present and past. Ishiguro creates a dragon Querig which is old and feeble, a composite creature with unmatched parts. She dragon has wings like a bird and eyes like a turtle. It is created by king Arthur to have a conservative force but this dragon becomes a problem to the people. The couple had to enter Querig's land, which was possessed by the she-dragon as the mother of Grendel in *Beowulf*. Wistan's quest is to slay the she dragon Querig as she is responsible for creating the mist that covers the land with amnesia. Father Jonus found that Querig caused the mass memory loss, due to "the mist." The "mysterious Island" "had become cursed with a mist of forgetfulness." The war is another greater cause for the memory loss, as "the thick mist" the symbol of forgetfulness covers the minds of the people so as to indulge in forgetfulness. The dragon Querig is not heroic because she is not the enemy. After Wistan killed Querig, the mist released memories with a few reverberations.

Memory carries both positive and negative sides which affected the protagonist Beatrice. Memories create will power and clarity, a clear way to focus their tasks. The other side memories create negative effect of fear, worries, shattering hopes, immorality, and guilty feelings. The couple believed very strongly that the bond between them is stronger despite their painful memories. "The christian monks leverage the act of forgetting in order to atone for the sins they have committed." Gawain reveals father Brian's treachery and has a feeling that the monks cast people to the beast in the tunnels because they know the mist will help them forget their sin. The entire novel is a challenging metaphor of the forgotten violence done by Arthur's soldiers upon innocent Saxons.

Mist is again used as a tool to keep up the collective forgetfulness with which the land suffers. But people were really happy as they forget others' misbehaviors and they forgive all ultimately. The couple was really happy before regaining the memory. When they are in their normal sense they could find out that they lost their son. So they started their journey to find out their son. They come to know about their bitter past. Their unfaithful relationship was opened. Axl is a Briton who lives on the outskirts of their Warren away from the communal fire that keeps everyone else

warm though they live in dark without even a candle. They are trying to bury their past to live their present. Their past was filled with worst atrocities. As they restored their memories, there is no better feeling.

Before the mist could close their memory again, the Britons had attacked a Saxon village in which Axl took part by revealing himself to Witson and Gawain. The journey was disrupted because of a rainstorm. When they took their refuge in the ruins, they happened to meet a boatman whose job is ferrying the persons from the mainland to the Island. As the couple getting ahead on each step, they find their recollections one by one. Loss of memory disappears as the mist disappears after the risen Sun. As Ishiguro himself told *The Paris Review*, “You do have to choose a setting with great care, because with a setting come all kinds of emotional and historical reverberations.” Reverberations via recollections help the couple to realize their mistakes in life, the quarrel between Axl and Beatrice gave way to Beatrice’s adultery. Though Axl proved to be a loving and caring husband, his ignoring of Beatrice made her indulge in adultery for which Axl felt sorry.

Ishiguro has created a boatman Charon, the mythical character who would take the couple to the other island, the symbolical representation of Heaven or hell. In Greek Mythology, Charon is the ferryman of Hades, who carries souls of the newly deceased across the river Styx and Acheron that divides the world of the dead. Here the boatman acts as Charon who agreed to take them across the river to see their son but with a condition that they should be “bonded by love.”

The strength of the couple’s bond (and thus their worthiness) is judged by boatmen who question the supplicants about their shared memories. In this afterlife, Charon is paid not in coins, but in memories. It eventually becomes clear that what is best for Beatrice and Axl might not be what is best for England, and the elderly couple must come to terms with their individual responsibility in the face of bleak and destructive consequences. (Teng)

The readers are not sure whether the couple is also alive or dead, whether it is their journey before death or after death. They recollect things as they move forward in their journey and get so much of reverberations in every move to identify their real position. The boat image can be compared to the ship image, one of the classical symbols for Christians, with a mast shown as a cross, a sign of hope, below the tempestuous waves. The couple contemplates with the problem of memory and loss as “memory is selective, necessary and haunting. Memories are unreliable and often painful but personal relationship can’t be forged without them” (Rambler). They cannot remember their past. Though they live in their past, they inhabit an eternal present.

Ishiguro identifies the difference between the human treachery, betrayal, and the threatening of animals. According to Karen, the novel depicts that how “honourable knights fight to the death for damsels in distress, they aspire to impossible perfection, and they are unfailingly earnest and uncynical” (Rambler). “Memory that is deliberately suppressed whether by the Britons generally or by our two main character preserves less that it destroys” (Rambler). Parents forget children and knights forget their orders.

In the second layer, the novel’s emphasis is on the historicity of story setting. The Buried Giant creates visual forms of winding lane or tranquil meadow, the land is desolate, rough paths over craggy hills or bleak moor land and ogres. The Buried Giant makes us understand the history of obliteration people. The Historical and social context is revealed as The Buried Giant is set at the time of a war between Saxons and Britons. New Historicism is the contingent, stressing note in the development of the story from the Sixth Century to the Modern themes of Memory loss and forgetfulness. In the course of the Journey, the couple encounters many adventures and battles with ogres, pixes, dragons and menacing soldiers. The characters took up challenges as “Cultural poetics” view the history of challenges and declared it to be subjective to provide with the final truth. The giant who was buried, “now stirs.” Ishiguro makes a clear picture of the war and its

destruction: “Men will burn their neighbors’ houses by nights. Hang children from trees dawns. The rivers will stink with corps bloated from their days of voyaging. And even as they move on, our armies will grow larger, swollen by anger and thirst for vengeance (324).”

Ishiguro is of the view that “Tolkien that what has been forgotten can be redeemed.” Tom Holland in his “The Buried Giant review Kazuo Ishiguro ventures into Tolkien Territory” in The Guardian says that “the shimmering of literary influences within Ishiguro’s prose is like that of memories within a fading mind: fragments shored against ruin. Yet always, haunting the novel, lurks the possibility that the memories themselves may be false.” The couple’s quest was not in vain: “The quest undertaken by Axl and Beatrice is not merely a search for their son, but one that follows in the footsteps of Sir Gawain, and Tennyson’s King Arthur, and Frodo” (Holland). Our modern civilization makes us feel elated with “what is new and present” is the ultimate happiness and thus make us dig our past history along with our past life.

Mary Carruther’s *The Book of Memory* (1990), offers fresh insights into the function of memory in the medieval world by drawing on instances relating to the role of memory in the works of Dante, Chaucer, and Aquinas to the symbolism of illuminated manuscripts. In the words of Carruthers, “The difference is that whereas now genius are said to have creative imagination which they express in intricate reasoning and original discovery, in earlier times they were said to have richly retentive memories, which they expressed in Intricate reasoning and original discovery” (58).

The result ends up in unleashing the greatest of treasures or even ends up in discovering the deadliest of sorrows leading to the darker shade of our psychological state, a miserable condition. The truth revealed or the moment of revelation instead of escalating into a state of triumph, buries the couple into deep sorrow. Certain secrets of the past are to be buried or to be drowned in the ocean of history so as to reach “being and becoming.” Euphoria, the momentous joyfulness stays till untangling the mystery. Let the mystery stay as mystery to celebrate the existing joy of life and instructing the phantom of emotions to bury the giant of sorrows and reverberations due to grieves soulfully to stand the test of time.

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